

Acidoid Behaviour of Charcoal as a Function of its Oxygen Complexes. Part VIII. Strength of Charcoal Acidoid

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Charcoals and carbon blacks associated with CO₂-complex can catalyse inversion of sucrose and hydrolysis of ethyl acetate. The rate constant of each reaction gives a measure of the H⁺ ion activity of the carbon used. The dissociation constant obtained from the data has about the same value irrespective of the nature of the carbon used or the type of the reaction studied. This shows that the same group or structure at carbon surface is responsible for surface acidity in charcoals and carbon blacks.

Surface acidity of carbons has formed the subject matter of several investigations and the subject has been reviewed recently by the senior author¹. The acidity has been attributed variously to the presence of carboxylic²⁻⁴, lactic³⁻⁵ or phenolic groups^{2,3,5} or merely to the presence of an oxide film in which two oxygen atoms are attached per active surface carbon atom^{6,7}. The studies reported so far have been restricted largely to the measurement of the quantity of acidity per g. while the intensity factor, i.e., the activity of H⁺ ions furnished by a carbon in aqueous suspension, has not received adequate attention. Direct measurements of pH values of aqueous suspensions by the usual potentiometric methods are associated, generally, with a certain degree of uncertainty. The other methods which suggest themselves are measurement of catalytic activity for the inversion of sucrose and for the hydrolysis of an ester such as ethyl acetate. The rate constants of these reactions at a given temperature are known to vary almost directly as the activity of H⁺ ions of the medium within a fairly wide range of pH between 0.5 to 4.0⁸. It was thought of interest, therefore, to determine the hydrogen ion activities of charcoal and carbon black suspensions by studying both the above reactions under standardised conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL

Charcoals prepared by the carbonisation of recrystallised cane sugar and coconut shells⁹ and rendered ash-free alongwith a few samples of carbon blacks were used in these investigations. The concentrations of sucrose and ethyl acetate (B.D.H., A.R. quality) in water (redistilled, CO₂-free) were fixed arbitrarily as 0.587M (20% w/v) and 1M, respectively, as these were found to be more convenient to work with. Several 1 g. portions of charcoal or carbon black (oven-dried at 120°) were mixed with 100 ml. portions of each solution contained in well-stoppered pyrex-glass bottles of 250 ml. capacity. The suspensions were allowed to stand with occasional shaking in an air-bath at a required temperature ($\pm 0.1^\circ$) for different intervals of time. The changes in concentrations of sucrose solutions

were determined polarimetrically by withdrawing a portion of the clear supernatant liquid while those of ethyl acetate solutions were determined by filtering the suspensions through glass wool, washing the residue with hot water to recover any acetic acid sticking to the charcoal or carbon black and then titrating an aliquot against a standard alkali in the usual way.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The inversion of sucrose and hydrolysis of ethyl acetate which do not take place to any noticeable extent at 40° in 24 hr. time in the absence of charcoal or carbon black are seen (Table I) to proceed to considerable extents on adding increasing amounts of original

TABLE I

Amounts of sucrose inverted and ethyl acetate hydrolysed at 40° in 24 hr. in the presence of sugar and coconut charcoals

Charcoal added		Amount of sucrose inverted (millimole)	Amount of ethyl acetate hydrolysed (millimole)
Sugar charcoal, original	0.5 g.	5.91	3.90
	1.0	8.00	5.65
	2.0	13.13	8.52
	3.0	15.22	12.51
	4.0	—	14.02
Sugar charcoal, outgassed at 750°	2.0 g.	0.11	0.13
Coconut charcoal, original	1.0 g.	4.76	3.14
	2.0	5.73	4.32
Coconut charcoal, outgassed at 750°	2.0 g.	0.08	0.06

sugar and coconut charcoals under similar conditions. The increase, however, is not in the same proportion as the weight of the charcoal. This is not to be expected since the catalytic effect is known to depend on the activity of H⁺ ions of the medium and not on the total acidity contained in it. This aspect will be referred to again shortly in this paper. It is interesting to note that the catalytic activity of each charcoal for each reaction disappears when it is outgassed at 750° so as to eliminate the entire amount of CO₂-complex even though appreciable amounts of the combined oxygen, being 3.4 and 3.1% for sugar and coconut charcoals, respectively, capable of evolving carbon monoxide were still retained by these materials. This again confirms the view that the acidity of carbons is due to the presence of CO₂-complex⁶⁷ and not to the total combined oxygen. Since surface area of charcoal is known to remain unchanged on evacuation upto 1000°¹⁰, the results show clearly that surface area is not a factor involved in catalysing these reactions at all.

The progress of each reaction with time, using 1 g. of sugar or coconut charcoal at 25° as well as at 40°, is shown by the data presented in Tables 2 and 3. Sugar charcoal is seen to be a better catalyst for each reaction and at each temperature. The plots of the values of $\log(a-x)$ versus t , the time in hours, at each temperature are shown in Fig. 1 and 2. The

Fig. 1. : Rate constants of inversion of sucrose at 25° and 45° using 1g. of sugar coconut charcoals as catalysts.

Fig. 2. : Rate constants of hydrolysis of ethyl acetate at 25° and 40° using 1g. sugar and coconut charcoals as catalysts.

curves show linear relationships, as expected. The rate constants, as obtained from the slopes of these curves are shown in the figures. The activation energy obtained by applying the Arrhenius equation were found to be about 19 and 14 K.cal/mole for the inversion of sucrose and hydrolysis of ethyl acetate, respectively, in the case of both the charcoals. These values are fairly close to those reported in the literature (20 and 16 Kcal/mole, respectively) when dilute acids are used as the catalysts¹¹.

TABLE 2

Amounts of sucrose inverted in the presence of 1 g. of original sugar and coconut charcoals, in 24 hr. at 25° and 40°

Time of contact (hours)	Amounts of sucrose inverted (millimole) at			
	25°		40°	
	In the presence of original sugar charcoal	In the presence of original coconut charcoal	In the presence of original sugar charcoal	In the presence of original coconut charcoal
4	0.16	0.04	1.51	0.79
8	0.61	0.15	2.83	1.82
12	1.18	0.52	4.25	2.40
24	1.83	1.16	8.00	4.76
48	3.60	2.31	15.00	9.15
72	5.49	3.38	21.12	14.32
96	7.15	4.44	26.61	18.25
120	8.84	5.65	30.75	21.42

The rate constants were then used for calculating activities of H⁺ ions of the various suspensions, knowing the relationship between the two, at 40°, as reported in the literature^{8,12} for the pH range 0.5 to 4.0.

The pH values thus obtained are recorded in Table 4. It is significant to note that the value for H⁺ ion activity of a given charcoal or carbon black suspension is almost the same irrespective of the fact whether it is obtained from the inversion of sucrose or hydrolysis of ethyl acetate. The pH values of the same suspensions, as obtained directly using glass electrode, are also included in the separate column in Table 4. These values are seen to be appreciably higher showing that the direct electrometric method does not measure the true intensity of acidity of charcoal or carbon black suspensions.

This view was checked in another way. Each reaction was allowed to take place for 5 days at 40° using 1 g. charcoal or carbon black. Sugar and coconut charcoals and seven samples of carbon blacks were included in these experiments. The extent of each reaction

TABLE 3

Amounts of ethyl acetate hydrolysed in the presence of 1 g. of original sugar and coconut charcoals in 24 hr. at 25° and 40°

Amounts of ethylacetate hydrolysed (millimole) at

Time of contact (hours)	25°		40°	
	In the presence of original sugar charcoal	In the presence of original coconut charcoal	In the presence of original sugar charcoal	In the presence of original coconut charcoal
4	0.15	0.14	0.71	0.21
8	0.36	0.27	1.85	0.74
12	0.70	0.36	2.96	1.31
24	1.85	1.32	5.65	3.14
48	3.61	2.42	9.84	6.76
72	5.35	3.50	15.35	9.66
96	7.05	4.63	19.13	12.71
120	8.73	5.65	24.01	15.68

TABLE 4

Rate constants in the presence of various charcoals and carbon blacks at 40° and the corresponding calculated pH values in comparison to determined pH values

Charcoal or carbon black added	Inversion of sucrose		Hydrolysis of ethyl acetate		pH value determined (glass-electrode)
	Rate constant $k \times 10^3$ (hr. ⁻¹)	pH value calculated	Rate constant $k \times 10^3$ (hr. ⁻¹)	pH value calculated	
Sugar charcoal, original	6.10	2.79	2.45	2.78	3.30
Coconut charcoal, original	3.74	3.00	1.44	3.01	4.00
Mogul	3.35	3.05	1.10	3.13	3.18
Mogul-A	2.79	3.13	0.94	3.19	3.25
ELF-O	1.50	3.40	0.57	3.42	3.83

is plotted against the corresponding pH value as obtained from catalytic activity as well as directly, in Fig. 3 and 4. It is evident that the points, in the first case, fit very well on smooth curves while those in the second case lie scattered all round.

Fig. 3 : Amounts of sucrose inverted ($40^{\circ}C$) using 1g. of various carbons as catalysts in relation to pH values.

The dissociation constant (K) of a weak acid can be obtained, knowing the activity of H^+ ions furnished by it at a given concentration (C), using the expression $K \approx a_H^2/C$, or $pK = 2pH + \log C$. It was thought of interest to use this equation for calculating dissociation constant of the acidoid in the case of the various charcoals and carbon blacks from their pH values recorded in Table 4 (columns 3 and 5). The values of C were obtained from their acidities as determined by the barium hydroxide method described elsewhere⁹. For example, the acidity of sugar charcoal was 6.7 millieq./g. Hence the values of C , when g. of this charcoal was added to 100 ml. of sucrose or ester solution, was taken as 0.067 mole per litre.

The pK values as obtained on using different samples of charcoal and carbon black and different weights of one of them are recorded in Table 5. It is highly significant to note that the values are of the same order and, in some cases, quite close to one another irrespective of the amount and nature of the carbon used or the type of catalytic reaction studied.

This strongly supports the view that it is the same acid group or structure which is responsible for surface acidity of charcoals and carbon blacks.

TABLE 5
Dissociation constant of the acidoid

Charcoal or carbon black added	Value of C (mole/litre)	pK value from		
		Inversion of sucrose	Hydrolysis of ethylacetate	
Sugar charcoal, original	: 0.5 g.	0.0335	4.382	4.425
	1.0	0.0670	4.406	4.386
	2.0	0.1340	4.233	4.329
	3.0	0.2010	4.261	4.150
	4.0	0.2680	—	4.170
Coconut charcoal, original	: 1.0g.*	0.0390	4.591	4.611
	Mogul	1.0g.*	4.214	4.374
	Mogul-A	1.0g.*	4.301	4.421
	ELF-O	1.0g.*	4.645	4.685

* The acidity values in the case of coconut charcoal, Mogul, Mogul-A and ELF-O were 3.9, 1.3, 1.1 and 0.7 millieq./g., respectively.

Fig. 4 : Amounts of ethyl acetate hydrolysed (40°C) using 1g. of various carbons as catalysts in relation to pH values.

The value of the dissociation constant is seen to be as high as that of benzoic acid. The view of some workers (*loc. cit.*) that surface acidity is due to the presence of such weakly acid groups as lactones does not appear to be correct. The presence of carboxyl groups also appears to be doubtful since the attachment of such groups to carbon crystallises, in view of Lewis base character of a bare carbon surface¹³, is unlikely to yield such strong acidoid character. It appears more reasonable to conclude, in conformity with the views of Strazhesko *et al.*¹⁴ in their work on oxidised coals, that H⁺ ion activity is due to the presence of an electrical double layer at the interface. The formation of such a double layer in the presence of CO₂-complex with H⁺ ions directed towards the liquid phase and the equivalent amount of negative charge left on the surface of carbon particles has already been suggested by Puri¹⁶.

REFERENCES

1. B. R. Puri, "Chemistry and Physics Carbon", Vol. VI, Edited by P. L. Walker, Jr., Marcel Dekker, Inc., New York, 1970.
2. M. L. Studebaker, E. W. D. Huffman, A. C. Wolfe and L. G. Nabors, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1956, **48**, 162.
3. H. P. Boehm, E. Diehl, W. Heck and R. Sappok, *Angew. Chem.*, 1964, **3**, 669.
4. J. B. Donnet, *Carbon*, 1968, **6**, 161.
5. V. A. Garten and D. E. Weiss, *Rev. Pure & Appl. Chem.*, 1957, **7**, 69.
6. B. R. Puri, G. Singh and L. R. Sharma, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **34**, 357.
7. B. R. Puri and R. C. Bansal, *Carbon*, 1964, **1**, 457.
8. R. P. Bell, "Acid-base catalysis", Oxford press, 1941, p. 13.
9. B. R. Puri, N. K. Sandle and O. P. Mahajan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 4880.
10. B. R. Puri, D. D. Singh and L. R. Sharma, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1958, **62**, 756.
11. E. A. Moelwyn-Hughes, "The kinetics of reactions in solution", Oxford Press, 1947, p. 57 and 324.
12. "International Critical Tables", Vol. VII, Edited by E. W. Washburn, McGraw-Hill Book Co. Inc. New York, 1930, p. 128 and 129.
13. M. L. Studebaker, *Rubber Chem. Tech.* 1957, **30**, 1400.
14. D. N. Strazhesko, Z. D. Skripnik, L. L., Charvyatsova and G. F. Vankovskaya, *Dokl.-Akad. Nau SSSR*, 1964, **155** (1) 169.